

OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE MANUFACTURING OF COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

The quality of sandwich structures was investigated for the out-of-autoclave prepreg processing method. The resin curing and rheological behaviour were characterized. The pressure inside a honeycomb core during cure was monitored. Representative sandwich panels were manufactured under different curing conditions and analyzed for quality.

Keywords: Sandwich structures, out-of-autoclave prepreg, resin characterization, composite manufacturing, honeycomb core pressure

INTRODUCTION

Autoclaves are used by the majority of commercial aircraft companies to manufacture composite structures. The quality of the resulting structure is usually excellent, however this quality comes with a very high infrastructure investment, and operating cost. Currently, out-of-autoclave (OOA) technology is being used to design and manufacture composite structural components at lower costs [1]. OOA technology enables composites to be produced using only vacuum pressure, eliminating the cost of purchasing and operating an autoclave. Perhaps a greater potential cost savings comes from the use of low temperature tooling, such as wood or syntactic foam [2].

The key to OOA prepreg is that they are specially designed to remove air that is entrapped during the lay-up process. The prepreg is partially impregnated creating a porous medium to evacuate any entrapped air before the resin becomes liquid and infuses the fibres [3]. When manufacturing sandwich structures with a honeycomb core, an additional volume of air is present. The effect of through thickness air permeability of prepreg skins to remove the air inside the core was studied by *Tavares et al.* [4]. They observed that if the internal core pressure is reduced, the fracture toughness between the skin and core increases, but the porosity of the composite skin also increases. The internal core pressure will determine the skin compaction pressure, which if insufficient, has been observed to cause voids in vacuum bag laminates [5].

Many factors contribute to the pressure inside the core, including the vacuum pressure, temperature profile, layup, and bagging arrangement. The objective of this study is to determine how these factors influence the pressure inside the core and the skin quality. The outcome will be used to design a cure cycle to manufacture a high quality sandwich panel using OOA technology.

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The first step towards designing a cure cycle is to characterize the curing and rheological behaviour of the resin. Prior to performing either of these tests, the thermal stability of the material must be understood to avoid degrading the material during cure. Once the upper temperature is known, the cure kinetics will provide the degree of cure of the resin after any cure cycle. As the temperature increases, the viscosity decreases and a competition begins between the softening and cross-linking of the polymer. The rheological performance of the resin will be used to select the optimal temperature ramp rate and dwell temperature. The resin viscosity can be controlled to keep the air paths in the prepreg open in order to remove entrapped air prior to the resin flowing.

The following sections will outline the materials used in this study, and the characterization of the resin. The first step is to determine the thermal stability of the resin, followed by the cure kinetics, and rheology. The test procedures will be outlined, and the results discussed for each step in the characterization.

Materials

The material used for the experiments was the Advanced Composites Group (ACG) MTM45-1 epoxy resin impregnated in a 5 harness satin carbon fabric. Neat resin film was used for cure kinetics and rheology testing, and prepreg with 36% resin content by weight was used for constructing the sandwich panels. The core material was a phenolic dipped Nomex honeycomb with a density of 73.5 kg/m^3 , 3.2 mm cell diameter, and 25 mm thickness.

Thermal Stability

A TA Instruments Q500 Thermal Gravimetric Analyzer (TGA) was used to measure the thermal stability of the resin materials. The testing procedure used was a standard ramp at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a nitrogen environment until 350°C . The weight loss is measured as a function of temperature, and an example of a typical TGA experimental result is shown in Figure 1. The resin is stable until 100°C , and then mass loss begins as the temperature increases. The mass loss represents volatiles that are escaping from the resin, and would need to be extracted from the prepreg, otherwise voids will occur.

Figure 1: Thermal stability analysis of the MTM45-1.

Cure Kinetics

A TA Instruments Q100 Dynamic Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) was used to measure the heat flow of the neat resin in dynamic and isothermal conditions. Dynamic scans at 2°C/min up to 250°C were conducted to determine the total heat of reaction of the resin. Isothermal tests were performed between 80°C and 180°C to determine the isothermal heat of reaction. Following the isotherm, the sample was cooled to room temperature and then ramped at 2°C/min to determine the residual heat of reaction. The residual heat of reaction is used as a check to ensure that the isothermal heat of reaction is accurate. The heats of reaction are calculated using the approach outlined by *Yousefi et al.* [6].

An isothermal scan at 120°C is shown in Figure 2. When the curing reaction is completed, at 6 hours in Figure 2, the degree of cure (α) is determined. The time required to achieve the maximum degree of cure (when $d\alpha/dt=0$) is now known for that temperature. The same approach was used for the other isothermal temperatures, and the results are summarized in Figure 3. This information is used to determine the hold time for the cure cycles used in the core pressure tests, and when manufacturing the representative panels.

Figure 2: Isothermal scan at 120°C.

Figure 3: Cure kinetics of MTM45-1 resin.

Rheology

The rheological behaviour of the neat resin was characterized using an AR 2000 Rheometer by TA Instruments. Dynamic and isothermal tests were used monitor the change in complex viscosity of the resin by inducing a small amplitude oscillatory strain in the sample between 25 mm parallel plates. A frequency sweep was conducted on the resin to ensure that the tests were in the linear viscoelastic region of the material. Subsequently, the rheology tests were conducted at a controlled strain of 0.1% and constant frequency of 1 Hz. The dynamic tests were performed at temperature ramp rates between 1-4°C/min. The isothermal tests were carried out between 80-180°C until the termination criteria, a complex viscosity > 10000 Pa-s, was met.

The rheological behaviour gives important information such the difference in minimum viscosity and the gel time for different hold temperatures. The dynamic rheological

behaviour of the resin is presented in Figure 4. The change in viscosity of the resin is independent of the 4 ramp rates until 120°C. The ramp at 1°C/min has the most noticeable difference in minimum viscosity compared to the ramps between 2-4°C/min. Based on this information, a ramp rate of 2°C/min was chosen for the core pressure and representative panels in-order to reduce the process variables. The isothermal rheological behaviour of the resin is presented in Figure 5. The graph shows the time available for the resin to flow, until a dramatic increase in complex viscosity occurs in a short period of time, known as the gel point. For multi-step cure cycles, the resin does not gel at 80°C within the first few hours. This slow curing behaviour is advantageous for 2 reasons. The first is that at 80°C the resin does not easily flow into the dry regions, allowing entrapped air to be removed. Secondly, if a higher dwell temperature is used after an intermediate hold at 80°C, the resin will continue to flow and infuse any dry regions of the fabric.

Figure 4: Dynamic viscosity response.

Figure 5: Isothermal viscosity response.

CORE PRESSURE MEASUREMENTS

The air entrapped inside the core is a crucial factor when manufacturing honeycomb structures. If the air entrapped during layup remains, it will expand during heating, and cause the composite skin to lift-off the cells. Also, diffusion of the air from the core into the skin will lead to voids if the air cannot be removed. Conversely, if all the air is removed, the pressure differential between the cells and the vacuum bag will reduce the amount of skin compaction, creating voids.

A test system to measure the pressure inside the honeycomb core was designed and manufactured based on the work of *Tavares et al.* [4]. A cross-section of the test fixture used to monitor the pressure inside the honeycomb cells during cure is shown in Figure 6. A pressure sensor is connected to the cavity where the honeycomb is contained, and the pressure inside the honeycomb cells is recorded as P_{cell} . At the same time, the vacuum pressure on the bag side of the prepreg skin is measured, and designated as P_{bag} . The entrapped air inside the honeycomb cavity, represented by the red dots in Figure 6, is pulled through the prepreg by the vacuum pressure applied on the bag side. When the

air reaches the composite skin, it is removed in the in-plane (represented by the red arrow in Figure 6), or through thickness direction.

Figure 6: Core pressure measurement test fixture.

When the air from the core reaches the skin, the bagging configuration will determine if the air travels in the through thickness direction, the in-plane direction, or both. The effect of three different release fabric/films was investigated, 1: polyester release fabric, 2: fluoropolymer release film with no perforations but microporosities, and 3: fluoropolymer release film with P3 perforation style. Since the polyester release fabric is very porous, the air would have no flow restrictions in the through thickness direction. However, the resin can also flow through the release film, increasing the likelihood of voids or dry spots. The release film with microporosities allows the air to flow through, but not the resin. Finally, the release film with P3 perforations may allow more air to flow through the skin, but also a small amount of resin.

The other parameters that were investigated include N: the number of plies, the vacuum pressure cycle, the temperature cycle, edge breathing, and the use of a film adhesive. The layout of the skin was $[0]_N$ for all the tests, where the 0-direction is parallel to the roll direction of the prepreg. Also, the vacuum pump was set between 10-20 kPa for all the tests, where 0 kPa is absolute vacuum. The time when full vacuum was applied was varied between the room temperature debulking step, the temperature ramp, and the beginning of the dwell. Varying when full vacuum was applied was used to determine if light vacuum pressure at room temperature would remove the entrapped air, and then increase the vacuum bag pressure at the beginning of the temperature ramp or dwell to 'lock in' the core pressure during cure. Finally, an edge breathing technique was investigated to see the influence on the skin quality. The edge breathing was similar to the one was used by *Repecka and Boyd* to improve the void content in out-of-autoclave prepreg [3]. The complete test matrix is shown in Table I.

Three specimens were cut from each test panel on a water cooled saw with a diamond cutting blade. The specimens were 60 mm in length, and were polished with an 800-grit silicon carbide sand paper using a rotational grinder/polisher. The void content in the

skin was determined for the samples using Image Tool 3.0 image processing software [7]. An image of the sample was scanned as a 24-bit colour image using a photo scanner with an optical resolution of 3200 dpi. The image was cropped to isolate the composite skin, and then converted to grayscale. A manual threshold was used to adjust the contrast such that the voids were differentiated from the skin, and an area analysis was performed to determine the percentage of voids in the skin. It should be noted that this analysis approach for comparative purposes, and only isolates the macrovoids greater than 50 μm in size. The microvoids are not captured, therefore underestimating the total void content in the skin.

Table I: Core Pressure Panel Test Matrix

<i>Test</i>	<i>No. Plies</i>	<i>Film Adh.</i>	<i>Edge Breath.</i>	<i>Release (type / plies)</i>	<i>RT Debulk (hr / kPa)</i>	<i>Full Vac Pressure Applied</i>	<i>Temp Cycle ($^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{hr}$)</i>
1	4	None	None	1 / 1	1 / 10	Debulk	130 / 3
2	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	0.5 / 50	Ramp	75 / 0.5 120 / 6
3	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	1 / 10	Debulk	75 / 0.5 120 / 6
4	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	0.5 / 50	Ramp	80 / 26
5	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	14 / 10	Debulk	180 / 2
6	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	1 / 10	Debulk	120 / 6
7	4	None	Yes	3 / 2	1 / 85	Dwell	120 / 6
8	4	None	None	3 / 2	2 / 10	Debulk	120 / 6
9	4	None	Yes	2 / 1	1.75 / 10	Debulk	75 / 0.5 120 / 6
10	2	Yes	Yes	2 / 1	1.5 / 10	Debulk	100 / 12
11	2	Yes	Yes	2 / 1	1 / 10	Debulk	75 / 0.5 120 / 6
12	2	Yes	Yes	2 / 1	1 / 10	Debulk	75 / 0.5 120 / 6
13	2	Yes	None	3 / 1	1 / 10	Debulk	100 / 12

Release Ply Types:

1. Polyester release fabric
2. Fluoropolymer release film with no perforations but microporosities, and
3. Fluoropolymer release film with P3 perforation style

The data collected during the core pressure measurement tests included the temperature of the test fixture, and the pressures inside the core and vacuum bag. Most of the tests had a consistent pressure in the core during cure, however the pressure inside the core of test 7 and 13 decreased during cure. The pressure and temperature plot of test 7 is shown in Figure 7, and test 8 is shown in Figure 8. In both tests, the initial pressure inside the cells falls towards the pressure inside the bag. A slight rise in pressure is observed as the temperature rises, as would be expected by the ideal gas law. However,

full vacuum pressure is applied at the beginning of the dwell in test 7, causing a large pressure gradient, and the air flow through the skin during the test. A similar behaviour is observed in test 13 (not shown) because of the P3 release film and no edge breathing. The lack of edge breathing did not remove the internal core pressure during the room temperature debulk, but the single ply of release film allows the air to flow during the test. The average pressure and the void content of the skin of each test are provided in Table II. A plot of the internal core pressures versus the void content in the skin is shown in Figure 9. This plot confirms that a higher void content is likely to occur when a low internal core pressure. Also, the internal core pressure for the majority of the tests was approximately 40 kPa.

Figure 7: Core pressure test 7.

Figure 8: Core pressure test 8.

Table II: Core Pressure Test Results

Test	P_{cell} (kPa)	Voids (%)
1	4	1.72
2	46	0.03
3	39	0.09
4	38	0.18
5	23	0.91
6	37	0.38
7	69	0.11
8	56	0.15
9	41	0.42
10	47	0.04
11	38	0.02
12	37	0.03
13	51	0.02

Figure 9: Void content as a function of the internal core pressure.

The quality of most of the panels was very good, with void contents less than 0.5%. However, test 1 and 5 were considerably worse. Test 1 had the highest void content because the release fabric allows the resin to flow out of the skin, and is absorbed by the

breather cloth. Since the initial resin content of the prepreg is 36%, the resin bleed caused sufficiently more voids to form in the skin, compared to the other tests. Test 5 showed the highest void content of all the panels cured with the fluoropolymer release films. The panel was debulked at room temperature overnight, creating a low internal core pressure. The panel was also cured at the highest tested temperature of 180°C, where more volatiles from the resin are escaping due to thermal degradation (Figure 1). The high temperature coupled with the low skin compaction creates an ideal breeding condition for voids. The other test variables were not clearly identified which configuration would lead to a better quality parts at this scale.

REPRESENTATIVE SANDWICH PANELS

The effect of scale-up may reveal processing issues that were not present in the good quality small panels, manufactured in the core pressure measurement fixture. Representative sandwich panels were manufactured using conventional techniques to identify if the bagging configuration, debulking cycle, and cure cycle would impact skin quality. The test matrix for the large sandwich panels is summarized in Table III.

Table III: Sandwich Panel Test Matrix

<i>Panel</i>	<i>Film Adhesive</i>	<i>Edge Breathing</i>	<i>Release Film (type / plies)</i>	<i>RT Debulking (hr / kPa)</i>	<i>Temp Cycle (°C / hr)</i>
1	Yes	Yes	2 / 1	2 / 10	100 / 12
2	Yes	Yes	2 / 1	12 / 10	100 / 12
3	Yes	Yes	3 / 1	9 / 10	80 / 24
4	Yes	None	2 / 1	2 / 10	80 / 2 & 140 / 2
5	Yes	Yes	3 / 2	3 / 40	75 / 2 & 120 / 6

Release Ply Types:

2. Fluoropolymer release film with no perforations but microporosities, and
3. Fluoropolymer release film with P3 perforation style

The 5 panels were manufactured in a Blue M convection oven, on a flat aluminum tool plate of 60 cm x 90 cm. A release agent was applied to the tool, opposed to using a release film. During layup, two plies of prepreg were placed on the tool, followed by 1 ply of film adhesive, the honeycomb core, another ply of film adhesive, and finally 2 more plies of prepreg. The panel size was 65 cm x 45 cm (Figure 10), including a 5 cm edge band. The core was cut with a 45° chamfer using a table saw. The layup of the skin was $[0/90]_{2s}$, where 0 is the roll direction of the prepreg, and the 0° plies are parallel to the 65 cm side. Microscopy samples of 60 mm were taken from the edge and centre of the panel as shown by the yellow lines in Figure 10. The void content in the skin was determined for the bag and tool side of both samples using the same technique as for the core pressure measurement tests, and the results are summarized in Figure 11.

The average void content and one standard deviation are reported for each panel. Panels 1 and 2 had the best quality. Both panels were bagged in the same configuration and cured at 100°C. The debulking time was varied to observe any effect on the void

content; the void content of the skins was equivalent. For panel 3, the cure temperature was decreased to 80°C to see the effect of high resin viscosity on part quality. A single ply of perforated release film was used to help remove air in the through thickness direction. Almost no resin flowed from the skin into the breather cloth, helping to keep a low void content in the skin. In panel 4, the edge breathing was removed, and the cure cycle had 2 holds for 2 hours, one at 80°C and 140°C. At a final dwell temperature of 140°C, volatiles were escaping from the resin (Figure 1), and the resin was able to reach its minimum viscosity (Figure 4), which also led to a short gel time (Figure 5). The short gel time may prevent the volatiles from being removed from the skin. The intermediate hold was successfully used with the smaller core pressure measurements to produce skins with a low void content, specifically in the 2-ply skin panels 11 and 12. Unfortunately, the intermediate hold was unable to remove the entrapped air and volatiles without the edge breathing in the larger representative panels. For panel 5, the vacuum pressure was set at 40 kPa and held for 3 hours at room temperature to set the internal core pressure. The vacuum was increased to full before the temperature cycle started. Similar to panel 4, an intermediate hold was used before reaching the final cure temperature. Panel 5 had the most resin loss of all the panels due to the perforated release film and high dwell temperature. Some resin flowed in-between the 2 plies of perforated release film, reducing the amount of resin available to impregnate the dry fibres in the skin. The resulting skin had the worst void content of all the panels.

Figure 10: Representative sandwich panel, showing the microscopy locations.

Figure 11: Void Content in the skin of the sandwich panels.

Figure 12: Cross section of the bag side in the centre of panel 1, showing the resin rich regions between the fibre tows.

Figure 13: Cross section of the bag side in the centre of panel 5, showing the voids.

Selected microscopy images at the centre of the bag side skins of panels 1 and 5 are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13, respectively. There are dark regions in between the fibre bundles are resin rich regions in Figure 12, in contrast to the voids that are present in Figure 13. The image processing software is capable of discerning the difference in contrast level between the resin rich regions and the voids.

CONCLUSION

Good quality sandwich structures can be manufactured using out-of-autoclave prepreg and vacuum bag curing techniques. The thermal degradation of the resin occurs above 100°C. If curing above this temperature, the escaping volatiles must be removed from the skin, otherwise voids will form. The time required to cure the resin to its fullest extent was determined for temperatures between 80-180°C. The optimal temperature ramp rate of 2°C/min, and the gel time for temperatures between 80-180°C were determined using a Rheometer. Upon completion of the thermal characterization of the resin, the effect of the temperature and pressure cycles, and the bagging configuration was investigated. Small scale sandwich panels were tested in a core pressure test fixture to identify the processing variables that dramatically reduced skin quality. The size of the core pressure measurement panels made it difficult to identify the subtle changes to the processing variables. Representative panels were manufactured, which identified that processing parts at temperatures above 100°C would lead to voids forming in the composite skin. Furthermore, curing the sandwich structure between 80-100°C will produce sandwich panels with void contents well below 1% with out of autoclave technology.

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